

INFLUENCE OF GENDER IN THE PROGRESSION OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

Ablyatifov Aziz Bakhtiyarovich
Pulatova Kristina Samvelovna

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10531966

Relevance: Chronic heart failure (CHF) is a serious problem for all developed countries of the world, despite significant progress in treatment, as the prognosis of these patients remains poor. This is primarily due to the aging of the population, as well as to the improvement of methods for the treatment of coronary heart disease (CHD), hypertension and other heart diseases that result in CHF. According to the latest recommendations of 2016, about 1-2% of the adult population of developed countries have CHF. At the age of 55, the risk of developing CHF during the rest of life is 33% in men and 28% in women. Within one year, 17% of hospitalized and 7% of stable (outpatient) patients with CHF die. The prognosis of CHF patients remains extremely poor: their risk of death is four times higher compared to those without CHF. Therefore, CHF is one of the main problems in modern gerontology and geriatrics and has a global socio-economic character.

Despite certain advances in pathogenesis, clinic, and treatment, this pathology is still the most common, severe, and prognostically unfavorable complication of all cardiovascular diseases. One of the main diseases of the second half of the 20th century is atherosclerosis and its consequences – hypertension, coronary heart disease (CHD) and chronic heart failure (CHF). The prevalence of clinically pronounced CHF in the Russian population is 5.5%, and if we take into account patients with asymptomatic left ventricular dysfunction (LV), then we can talk about 11.7% of the population. There is a clear upward trend in the number of CHF patients worldwide. In the next 50 years, it is XCN that will become the main problem of cardiology.

The purpose of the study: To conduct a clinical and laboratory comparative assessment of the ratio of women and men among patients with CHF hospitalized in the Samarkand branch of the republican scientific center of emergency medical care.

Material and methods: On the basis of the Samarkand branch of the republican scientific center of emergency medical care, we conducted a survey of 30 patients with detected CHF aged 50-65 years. Of these, 17 are men and 13 are women, which is 56.7% and 43.3%, respectively. Depending on gender, the patients were divided into 2 groups: group 1 consisted of men, group 2 women. The severity of CHF was determined in these patients according to NYHA (1964). CHF II FC was registered in group 1 in 10 (58.8%) patients, in group 2 in 8 (61.5%) patients. CHF III FC was determined in the 1st group in 7 (41.1%) patients, in the 2nd group in 5 (38.4%) patients.

Results: Hypertension – II with a moderate risk of developing with LVH as a risk factor for the development of CHF in 63% of patients was significantly more often registered in men than in women. Stage III hypertension with high development with LVH and with a history of PICS in 27% of cases caused the formation of stage II B CHF (NYHA III FC). Thus, in patients with hypertension, the incidence of CHF increases in the population of patients with hypertension of II and III degrees, while the number of patients with CHF of higher functional classes increases. In men, CHF is three times more common than in women, but at the age of 70 years

or more, the ratio of men to women is almost equalized. The combination of AH, LVH and PICS is more common in men. The presence of at least the following three signs was the basis for the establishment of stage II A CHF (NYHA II FC). Shortness of breath at the slightest physical exertion. Prior to admission to separate emergency therapy No. 1, the patients were regularly treated with diuretics. One of the following signs was present - congestion in the lungs (on radiograph) - Auscultatively wet crackles in the lungs. - listening to the third tone of the heart - edema in the lower extremities - entrapment of the liver with less than 2 cm from under the costal arch - swelling of the cervical veins, persisting in the standing position; - Cardiothoracic index of more than 0.5 cm. - ECG changes (cicatricial changes, LVH, heart rhythm and conduction disorders). - Registration of LV LV less than 54%. In patients with CHF, the following indicators were revealed during blood analysis: creatinine in patients in group 1 was 115.17 ± 26.4 mmol/l, in group 2 was 117.3 ± 48.32 mmol/l, residual nitrogen in group 1 was 21.43 ± 6.46 mmol/l, in group 2 was 22.50 ± 6.72 mmol/l, urea in the 1st group was 7.4 ± 2.3 mmol/l, in the 2nd group was 7.8 ± 2.9 mmol/L. Depending on the severity of stress in group 1, 8 (47%) patients had severe stress, 4 (23.5%) patients had moderate stress, 5 (29.5%) patients had no stress, in group 2, 4 (30.7%) patients had severe stress, 3 (23%) of patients had moderate stress, 6 (46.3%) patients had no stress.

Conclusions: Thus, our studies have shown that male patients are more prone to severe CHF, as they had statistically significantly increased creatinine, residual nitrogen and urea, as well as among men, the occurrence of stress and its progression is significantly pronounced than in women. Perhaps this is due to an incorrect lifestyle and diet, which requires further research.

References:

1. Abdulloeva M., Pulatova K., Mirzaev R. ORTIQCHA VAZN VA ARTERIAL GIPERTONIYA BILAN OG'RIGAN YOSHLARDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN JINSIY ZAIFLIK //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2023. – T. 3. – No. 4 Part 2. – pp. 91-94.
2. Pulatova K. S. INFLUENCE OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS ON INSULIN RESISTANCE AND LIPID SPECTRUM INDICATORS // European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development . – 2023. – T. 15. – P. 72-75.
3. Dilshodovna AM, Odylovna KF, Samveilovna PK Peculiarities of Psychological Disorders in Patients with Acute Coronary Syndrome //International Journal of Health Systems and Medical Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – No. 6. – pp. 203-207.